

ESTIMATES OF GENETIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL VARIABILITY IN SESAME (*Sesamum indicum* L.)P. Maheetha^{1*}, J. E. Jahagirdar², P. B. Wadikar³¹Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Latur.²Ex-Director of Research, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.³Associate Professor, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Latur.pudimaheetha36381@gmail.com

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Abstract

Sesame is an important oilseed crop which belongs to the family Pedaliaceae and is known as the “Queen of oilseed crops”. Genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance were evaluated for 38 sesame genotypes for ten different traits viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, days to maturity, plant height, number of branches per plant, number of capsules per plant, capsule length, number of seeds per capsule, 1000 seed weight, oil content and seed yield per plant during summer 2023. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed significant variation among the genotypes for all the characters studied. The PCV values are slightly higher than the GCV values for the characters studied indicating the environmental influence on the expression of such traits. Simple phenotypic selection may be effective for the traits exhibiting high heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percent of mean which is shown by the characters like seed yield per plant, capsule length and number of capsules per plant indicating that, heritability is most likely due to additive gene action. The trait, days to maturity recorded high heritability along with low genetic advance as percent of mean indicating the presence of non-additive gene action. Selection is not effective as high heritability is due to favourable influence of environment rather than genotype.

Keywords: Variability, Heritability, Genetic advance, GCV, PCV, Sesame.

Introduction:

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) $2n=26$, belongs to the family *Pedaliaceae* and is one of the oldest cultivated oilseed crops. Sesame is referred to as the “Queen of oilseed crops” because of the antioxidative property of its oil. India is the second largest producer of sesame in the world next to Sudan. Major states growing sesame in India are West Bengal, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. Area of sesame is on decline from 13.44 lakh hectare in 2022-23 to 12.43 lakh hectare in 2023-24 for *kharif* sown crop and from 0.27 lakh hectare in 2022-23 to 0.16 lakh hectare in 2023-24 under *rabi* season. (The TN-agritech.tnau.ac.in).

For any breeding programme of any crop, variability is a pre-requisite for selection. It is used for development of new lines and these developed lines with desired variability can be used as parents in the further breeding programme. Direct selection is not effective as it involves environmental factors and there will be influence of other traits. So, it is necessary to study genetic variability with respect to quantitative traits and genetic parameters like genotypic and phenotypic variances, heritability (broad sense) and genetic advance to evolve appropriate selection indices and exertion of selection. When the necessary genetic variability is present, selection can be done for that character.

Materials and methods:

The present investigation was carried out at Oilseed Research Station, Latur during *summer*, 2023. The experimental material comprises of 34 genotypes along with 4 checks. Each genotype is sown in two rows with a spacing of 45 cm between the rows and 10 cm between the plants in a Randomised Block Design (RBD) with two replications. Necessary agronomic measures are carried out for the experimental units. Mean performance of all the genotypes were recorded from five randomly selected plants in each plot of each genotype. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is carried out by the formula given by Panse and Sukhatme (1954). Phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) and genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) were estimated according to the method proposed by Burton (1952). PCV and GCV ranges were estimated as low (0-10%), moderate (10-20%) and high (>20%) by Sivasubramanian and Madhavamenon (1973). Genetic advance was evaluated by the procedure estimated by Johnson *et al.* (1955) and heritability in broad sense was calculated by the formula proposed by Hanson *et al.* (1956).

Results and Discussion:

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is represented in Table 1 which showed that, there is significant variation among the genotypes for all the characters studied.

Mean performance along with variability, heritability and genetic advance values of each trait are shown in Table 2. The phenotypic

coefficient of variation (PCV) values are higher than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) values indicating that there is influence of environment. The values of PCV ranged from 3.62 (days to maturity) to 29.57 (seed yield per plant), whereas GCV values ranged from 3.04 (days to maturity) to 26.77 (seed yield per plant). Higher values of GCV and PCV were observed for seed yield per plant indicating the presence of considerable amount of genetic variability and less influence of environment and suitable for selection, moderate values for the traits *viz.*, capsule length, number of capsules per plant, number of branches per plant and 1000 seed weight. Whereas, lower values were recorded for the characters such as number of seeds per capsule, plant height, days to 50 per cent flowering, oil content and days to maturity which showed low range of variability with influence of environment and unsuitable for selection. Similar findings of higher GCV and PCV were reported by Mahla *et al.* (2024), Rahna *et al.* (2023), Hemanth and Patil (2023), Thiyagu *et al.* (2023), Kumar *et al.* (2022) and Sasipriya *et al.* (2022). Lower GCV and PCV values are in accordance with Rahna *et al.* (2023), Chandawar *et al.* (2023) and Takele *et al.* (2023).

Heritability estimates indicate how traits are passed on from parents to their progeny. The values of heritability (%) ranged from 48.73 (number of seeds per capsule) to 95.60 (oil content) whereas, the estimates of genetic advance as percent of mean (%) are in the range of 5.27 (days to maturity) to 49.94 (seed yield per plant). Estimates of heritability along with estimates of genetic advance are more useful in choice of selection method rather than heritability or genetic advance alone (Johnson *et al.* 1955). The characters seed yield per plant, capsule length and number of capsules per plant showed high heritability coupled with high genetic advance as per cent of mean which indicated that heritability is most likely due to additive gene effects and simple phenotypic selection may be effective. Similar results are obtained by Mahla *et al.* (2024) and Rahna *et al.* (2023). High heritability with moderate genetic advance is exhibited by oil content followed by days to 50 per cent flowering which showed these traits are controlled by both additive and non-additive gene action rather than by environment and hence reciprocal recurrent selection must be followed for improving these traits. Results are in accordance with Hemanth and Patil (2023) and Rahna *et al.* (2023). The trait days to maturity recorded high heritability coupled with low genetic advance as per cent of mean which indicated the presence of non-additive gene action. Hence, heterosis breeding will be rewarding for further improvement. High heritability is due to favourable influence of environment rather than genotype and selection for such trait may not be rewarding. Similar results are obtained by Mitkari *et al.* (2023). Moderate heritability with moderate genetic advance as per cent of mean were observed for

number of branches per plant and 1000 seed weight that indicated the involvement of non-additive gene action and selection might not be effective. Results are in accordance with Sootrakar *et al.* (2022). Other traits like plant height and number of seeds per capsule showed moderate heritability with low genetic advance as per cent of mean which showed that the traits were highly influenced by environmental effects and governed by non-additive gene action. Similar results were recorded by Takele *et al.* (2023).

Therefore, from the present study it can be concluded that, the traits seed yield per plant, number of capsules per plant and capsule length were controlled by additive gene action suggesting that these traits can be improved by simple selection. Traits such as oil content and days to 50 per cent flowering were under the influence of non-additive gene action and appropriate breeding and selection strategy should be employed in selection of these traits.

Conclusion:

The characters with high GCV and PCV was exhibited by seed yield per plant whereas heritability is highest for oil content, capsule length, number of capsules per plant, days to 50 per cent flowering, days to maturity and seed yield per plant and high genetic advance as per cent of mean is observed for seed yield per plant, capsule length and number of capsules per plant. Simple selection can be applied on the genotypes with high variability and these genotypes can be used in the future.

References:

1. **Burton, G. W. 1952.** Quantitative inheritance in grasses. In: Proceedings of 6th International Grassland Congress, Pennsylvania State College, USA, 23 August 1952, pp. 277-283.
2. **Chandawar, P. N., Manapure, P. R., Patil, S. R., Shende, P. V., Shinde, J. G., Madke, V. S & Gujar, M. G. 2023.** Genetic variability studies in semi *rabi* local germplasms of sesame. *Journal of soils and crops*, 33(1): 184-189.
3. **Gaurav Gautam1 , Prof. (Dr.) Suresh, B.G.2 Amit Malav3 , Sunil Kumar, 2018,** Study On Genetic Variability In Greengram (*Vigna radiata* L. WILCZEK), VOL. VIII, ISSUE SPECIAL(E) , August 2018 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 82-87.
4. **Hanson, G H., Robinson, H. F., & Comstock, R. E. 1956.** Biometrical studies of yield segregating population of Korean lespedeza. *Agronomy Journal*, 48: 268-272.
5. **Hemanth, S., & Patil, L. C. 2023.** Selection index and genetic variability for morpho-phenological traits in sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 12(6), 1880-1883.
6. **Johnson, H W., Robinson, H. F., & Comstock, R. E. 1955.** Estimates of genetic and environmental variability in soyabean. *Agronomy Journal*, 47: 314-318.
7. **J.P. Khatod1 , S.J. Gahukar1*, V. J. Dhole2 and P. Kadirvel, 2024,** Optimization Of Treatments Of Gamma Rays And Ems To Induce Genetic Variability In Safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius* L.), VOL. XIV, ISSUE XXXXX, Feb. to April. 2024, Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 172-175.

8. **Jyoti Singh * And Shubha Banerjee, 2019,** Understanding The Genetic Variability In Rice Genotypes Belonging To C.G. Region In Relation To Chloroplast Genome, VOL. VIII, ISSUE XXVIII, JAN 2019 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 250-257.
9. **Kumar, V., Sinha, S., Sinha, S., Singh, R. S., & Singh, S. N. 2022.** Assessment of genetic variability, correlation and path analysis in sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *Electronic Journal of Plant Breeding*, 13(1), 208-215.
10. **M.M. Pandya1*, P.B. Patel2 , A.V. Narwade3 And B.N.Patel1, 2016,** Genetic variability in Sunflower, (*Helianthus annuus* L), VOL. VI, Issue XVI, April 2016 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 146-149.
11. **Mahla, N. U., Jagtap, P. K., & Patel, H. R. 2024.** Genetic variability and association among yield and yield related traits of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) genotype. *International Journal of Plant & Soil Science*, 36(2), 197-206.
12. **Mitkari, S. B., Wankhade, M. P., Ghuge, S. B., Kute, K. G. & Deshmukh, A.A. (2023).** Genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance studies in sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 12(12): 1345-1348.
13. **Panse, V. G. and Sukhatme, P. V. 1954.** Statistical methods for agricultural workers. 1st Edn. pp. 280-297. Indian Council of Agricultural Research. New Delhi.
14. **Rahna, K., Kalaiyarasi, R., Umadevi, M., Senthil, A. & Sudha, M. 2023.** Genetic variability and diversity analysis in sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) germplasm. *Electronic Journal of Plant Breeding*, 14(3), 1055-1062.
15. **Sasipriya, S., Parimala, K., Balram, M., & Eswari, K. B. 2023.** Assessment of genetic diversity in sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) for yield and its components. *International Journal of Bio-resource and Stress Management*, 14(3), 443-449.
16. **Sivasubramanian, S & Madhavamenon, P. 1973.** Genotypic and phenotypic variability in rice. *Madras Agricultural Journal*, 60: 1093-1096.
17. **Sootrakar, K., Payasi, S. K., Joshi, R. P., & Pandey, S. 2022.** Estimation of genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance for the phenotypic traits in sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.).
18. **Takele, F. & Abera, G. 2023.** Variability study in ethiopian sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) genotypes at Western Oromia. *International Journal of Precision Farming*, 1(1), 1-7.
19. **Thiyagu, K., Dhandapani, M., Geethanjali, S., Sathya, P., Shanmugam, A., Subrahmaniyan, K. & Salini, A. P. 2023.** Assessment of genetic variability, correlation and traits association in sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.). using F₄ families under summer rice fallow conditions. *The Pharma Innovation Journal* 12(5): 1330-1335.

Table 1: ANOVA for yield and yield contributing traits in sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.).

Source of variation	Replication	Treatment	Error
D.F	1	37**	37
Days to 50 per cent flowering	2.22	17.54**	2.84
Days to maturity	0.32	19.64**	3.38
Plant height (cm)	7.57	106.3**	35.86
No. of branches per plant	0.30	0.57**	0.16
No. of capsules per plant	1.77	103.86**	15.83
Capsule length(cm)	0.004	0.48**	0.030
No. of seeds per capsule	0.013	42.38**	14.60
1000 seed weight (g)	0.021	0.157**	0.051
Oil content	0.67	14.74**	0.33
Seed yield per plant (g)	0.004	8.57**	0.84

* and ** indicates significance at 5% level and 1% level respectively.

Table 2: Mean, variances, Coefficient of variances, Heritability, Genetic advance and Genetic advance as percent of mean for various characters.

Sr. No.	Name of the character	Mean	GV (σ^2g)	PV (σ^2p)	EV (σ^2e)	GCV	PCV	ECV	Heritability (%)	Genetic advance	GAM (%)
1	Days to 50 per cent flowering	43.82	7.35	10.20	2.85	6.18	7.28	3.85	72.09	4.74	10.82
2	Days to maturity	93.59	8.13	11.51	3.38	3.04	3.62	1.97	70.61	4.94	5.27
3	Plant height (cm)	102.09	35.25	71.12	35.86	5.81	8.26	5.87	49.56	8.61	8.43
4	No. of branches per plant	4.22	0.20	0.37	0.17	10.67	14.36	9.61	55.25	0.69	16.34
5	No. of capsules per plant	51.17	44.10	59.95	15.85	12.96	15.11	7.78	73.53	11.73	22.90
6	Capsule length (cm)	2.69	0.23	0.26	0.03	17.60	18.77	6.50	88.00	0.92	34.03
7	No. of seeds per capsule	55.93	13.89	28.50	14.61	6.66	9.54	6.83	48.73	5.36	9.58
8	1000 seed weight (g)	3.00	0.05	0.10	0.05	7.67	10.74	7.52	50.98	0.34	11.28
9	Oil content	46.64	7.21	7.54	0.33	5.75	5.88	1.23	95.60	5.41	11.59
10	Seed yield per plant (g)	7.34	3.86	4.71	0.85	26.77	29.57	12.56	81.97	3.67	49.94

GV-Genotypic variance, PV-Phenotypic variance, EV-Environmental variance, GCV-Genotypic coefficient of variation, PCV-Phenotypic coefficient of variation, ECV-Environmental coefficient of variation, GAM-Genetic advance as percent of mean.

Fig 1: Genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation

Fig 2: Heritability and genetic advance as per cent of mean